

Overview on Labor Productivity

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Abstract:

Labor productivity is a determining factor to competition capacity of economies in general and enterprises in particular, especially in developing countries like Vietnam. In order to catch up with labor productivity of other countries, Vietnam needs to change growth model based on labor productivity, quality and efficiency, in which focusing on improving labor productivity. Enterprises account for a large share of GDP and play an important role in labor productivity enhancement of almost of economies.

Keywords: Labor productivity

1. Introduction

In the context of international integration and strict competitiveness, labor productivity is a determining factor to competition capacity of economies in general and enterprises in particular. Productivity is a key driver of long-term economic growth. Labor productivity enhancement is vital for all developing countries because it ensures rapid and sustainable development, helping the country escape from middle income trap, and catching up with other nations in the region. Recognizing the importance of labor productivity in enhancing competitive ability of every countries, most countries has paid attention to improve labor productivity by enacting specific policies, strategies and plans to increase labor productivity.

In Vietnam, labor productivity is fairly good compared to other countries in the region. It has steadily increased over the years and has certain differences between economic sectors in which labor productivity in the enterprise sector is more than three times higher than the national average of the economy. Improving and promoting labor productivity have been one of the key issues of the Vietnamese economy.

Enterprises account for a large share of GDP and play an important role in labor productivity enhancement of the economy. The real situation of labor productivity of Vietnam's enterprises is lower than other countries in the region in terms of some key aspects. SMEs play vital roles in the economic development of all countries, especially in stimulating productivity and industrial growth. In addition to their significant contributions to GDP, enterprises must embrace technology and innovation to approach sustained productivity performance in the current volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous environment.

2. Literature review

As a category to enhance competitive capacity, labor productivity improvement quite received much attention and researches from many organizations and researchers, including the researches on national productivity improvement of economy in general, on labor productivity improvement of enterprise sector, in particular.

Regarding to studies of productivity in general, it would be impossible not to mention on the book "APO Productivity Databook 2019", by Asia Productivity Organization. This is an annual analytical report on recent and long-term productivity and economic performance in the Asia-Pacific, details the diverse stages and pace of economic development of member countries as well as reference economies. Productivity measurement based on official data enables relevant comparisons of the quality of economic growth and productivity gains achieved. International comparisons and analyses are the basis for evidence-based policy advisory services offered by the APO to member countries. The Enhancing SME Productivity: Policy highlights on the role of managerial skills, workforce skills and business linkages by the author group of OECD includes: Marco Marchese, OECD, France; Elisa Giuliani, University of Pisa, Italy; Juan Carlos Salazar-Elena, Autonomous

University of Madrid, Spain; and Ian Stone, University of Durham, United Kingdom. The paper shows productivity gaps by firm size and productivity gaps change significantly depending on the specific size and sector of the firm and factors internal to the firm that directly affect SME performance. Then the paper focuses on how they affect SME productivity and what policies work best in labor productivity SMEs leverage these drivers. Besides that, some papers and reports of international organizations such as: ADB, ILO, UNIDO, WB, etc. mention to the labor productivity of enterprises and other sectors.

Some significant research on productivity in Japan such as: Productivity Drag from Small and Medium- Sized Enterprises in Japan by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) with authors: Mariana Colacelli and Gee Hee Hong Authorized for distribution by Paul Cashin. The paper finds supportive evidence for the important role of SMEs in explaining Japan's modest productivity growth. The white paper of SMEs in Japan in 2018, analyzes recent SME trends and examines the labor productivity and management of SMEs. Based on the information collected, the paper discusses the initiatives of SMEs to improve productivity, with a focus on their review of work processes, initiatives for the effective use of human resources, introduction of IT, capital investment and business restructuring and integration.

For the productivity of China, it is not impossible if I don't write here "Thriving on a Tilted Playing Field: China's Non-State Enterprises in the Reform Era" by Chong-En Bai University of Hong Kong David D. Li Hong Kong University of Science and Technology and CEPR Yijiang Wang University of Minnesota and CEPR. The seeks to address three related questions relating to the non-state enterprises develop rapid and get achievements in China during period 1978-1999. The paper suggested that China's governments need to implement further reforms to level the playing field in order to sustain the vitality of the non- state sector. The "Privatization and Productivity in China" by Yuyu Chen, Mitsuru Igami, Masayuki Sawada, Mo Xiao Jan 31, 2018. The paper confirmed that Privatization has boosted Chinese firms' productivity, both in the short run and the long run. Consumer-oriented industries saw larger gains than "strategic" (heavily regulated) sectors.

In Vietnam, there are also some studies on the labor productivity. It is impossible not mentioned to a range of papers and reports of ministries and researchers at the Conference on National labor productivity improvement on August 2019. Of which, some papers are highly appreciated: Article "Labor productivity and key solutions to enhance labor productivity in Vietnam" of Ministry of Planning and Investment; the report "Contribution of science, technology and innovation to productivity enhancement", of Ministry of Science and Technology; the paper: "New business model and its impact on labor productivity" of the Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences. These papers outlined general situation, factors impact on labor productivity in Vietnam. They also provide the basic analysis on labor productivity in comparisons among sectors, emphasized role of innovation creation, technology in improving labor productivity, then proposes some solutions to enhance labor productivity in Vietnam.

The study on "Productivity and Competitiveness of Vietnam's Enterprises" by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) published in April 2019, was conducted by the group of experts: Dr. Nguyen Thang (Centre for Analysis and Forecast (CAF), Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences (VASS)) was the team leader responsible for the study's methodology, analytical framework and consolidation of team members' inputs, Dr. Le Van Hung (Vietnam Economics Institute, VASS) and Dr. Nguyen Anh Tuan (Vietnam Productivity Institute - VNPI, Ministry of Science and Technology - MOST), Dr. Nguyen Do Anh Tuan and Dr. Truong Thi Thu Trang, Ms. Nguyen Thi Thuy, Ms. Nguyen Thi Thuy An, Ms. Ngo Thi Mai (Institute of Policy and Strategy for Agricultural and Rural Development (IPSARD), Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MARD)) and Dr. Luong Van Khoi and Dr. Tran Toan Thang (National Centre for Socio-Economic Information and Forecast, NCIF), Ministry of Planning and Investment (MPI), Dr. Nguyen Ngoc Anh (Development and Policies Research Centre, DEPOCEN), an Enterprise Census data analysis by the NCIF team and Mr. Vu Hoang Dat (CAF), Dr. Nguyen Thang and Mr. Nguyen Tien Phong (UNDP) based on the draft report prepared by Dr. Le Van Hung and additional inputs from Mr. Vu Hoang Dat (CAF) and Dr. Cengiz Cihan (UNDP). This study includes three volumes: 1, 2, 3 with three sectors: manufacturing, agriculture and services, respectively. The

study reflects and analyses current situation of labor productivity in three key economic sectors in Vietnam by both metric economic and qualitative methodology. It also suggests solutions for labor productivity improvement in mentioned sectors.

Besides the mentioned research above, in Vietnam there are several studies on labor productivity, such as: “Overall on labor productivity in construction sector” by Nguyen Duc Loi, Thuyloi University and Ta van Phan, Haiphong University,.. However, these studies mainly focus on key economic sectors for the whole economy but not focus on enterprises especially non-state enterprises that accounts for more than 90% share of total enterprises and employment in Vietnam.

3. Labor Productivity Theory

3.1. Definition on labor productivity

Labor productivity reflects the capacity to create property, the labor efficiency in the production process, measured by number of products or output generated in a unit of time or the amount of time used to produce one unit of product.

Labor productivity = $\frac{\text{Gross domestic products (GDP)}}{\text{Total average number of laborers}}$

Total average number of laborers

The inputs include capital, labor, machine, components, equipment's, raw, materials, etc. The outputs are measured by products, turnover, value added of outputs, etc.

Per-hour labor productivity is labor productivity measures the hourly output of a country's economy. Specifically, it charts the amount of real gross domestic product (GDP) produced by an hour of labor. Growth in labor productivity depends on three main factors: saving and investment in physical capital, new technology, and human capital.

3.2. Theories of labor productivity

3.2.1. Adam Smith's theory of labor productivity

Term “Yield” was used for the first time by Adam Smith in 1776, until the end of 19th century when workers were replaced by machinery, the meaning of productivity was widely known. While emphasizing the elements of input, especially labor, Yield could be understood as labor productivity.

Currently, there are many different concepts of productivity, that in general define productivity as the ratio between used input over output and can be indicated by formula: $\text{Productivity} = \frac{\text{Output}}{\text{Input}}$. Inputs can be calculated according to the number of employees, capital or labor time consumption, frequent cost. Output is often calculated by gross domestic product as at local and national economy level, and by value added at industry or enterprise level. Productivity can be calculated for national or local economy, industry or enterprise, each activity, etc.

3.2.2. Cobb-Douglas's theory of labor productivity

Cobb-Douglas theorized about the behavior of producers through production functions to thereby find ways to increase production for the economy. He pointed out the importance of capital, labor and science and technology to economic growth in general and labor productivity in particular. Accordingly, the prerequisite factors affecting productivity labor is the human and capital. Without human, there's no need to mention productivity. Without capital, the production process cannot take place, let alone high or low productivity.

Cobb-Douglas argued that the relationship between the number of inputs and the number of outputs (products) produced by the production process was represented by the production function. Accordingly, the production

function is defined as a function that indicates the dependence of output on the inputs. In other words, in the production function, the dependent variable (or the explanatory variable) is the output, while the independent variable (or the explanatory variable) is the input levels.

In microeconomics, production function indicates an amount of products that manufacturers produce from factors of production such as capital, labor, etc... In macroeconomics, the production function expresses the value of gross domestic product depending on the number of labor, the amount of capital, and the technology of an economy.

The production function is usually in Cobb-Douglas form as follows: $Y = A\alpha K\beta$,

in which:

Y = output

L = number of labor input K = amount of capital

A = total factor productivity

α and β are the elasticity according to the output respectively of labor and capital; which are fixed and determined by technology.

If $\alpha + \beta = 1$, then the production function has a constant return to scale, meaning that even if labor and capital increase by 20% each, the output will only increase by exactly 20%.

If $\alpha + \beta < 1$, then the production function has return decreasing by scale. If $\alpha + \beta > 1$, the production function has return increasing by scale.

In case of the market (or economy) in perfect competition state, α and β can be considered as the contribution of labor and capital to output.

In addition to the Cobb-Douglas form, the production function can also be in the form of fixed coefficients and the form of fixed replacement elasticity.

3.2.3. Solow's theory of labor productivity

Solow talked about the theory of long-term economic growth. However, through that theory, he indirectly proposed a method to increase labor productivity for the economy in general and for enterprises in particular. Solow growth model indicates the impact of savings, the rate of population growth and technological progress for the growth of the output of an economy as time goes by.

Solow gave the production function as follows: $Y = F(K, L)$

From this function, he drew that there were three sources of possible long-term economic growth.

First, the volume of capital can be increased over time. Secondly, the number of employees may change over time due to population changes. Thirdly, the production function itself can be changed over time by the progress of science and technology.

Although labor productivity increases when the ratio of capital to labor increases, the marginal productivity of capital tends to decrease as labor productivity increases. Solow said that in the short term, labor productivity increases as capital accumulation per capita increases. In the long run, the economy will move towards a state of equilibrium and long-term growth. At that time, the growth rate of output will be equal to the growth rate of science and technology factors plus the growth rate of labor (population). That is, labor productivity of the economy will grow at the same rate as that of science and technology.

3.2.4. Marx's theory of labor productivity

According to Marx, labor productivity is the productivity of specific useful labor, measured by the number of products produced in a given unit of time. Labor productivity reflects the efficiency of labor use, the relationship between output (products) and input (labor), as measured by the amount of time to do work, in other words reflects the performance level of employees.

Labor productivity is an important indicator to show the nature and level of advancement of an organization, a production unit, or a means of production. Labor productivity is determined by many factors such as skill level of workers, the level of scientific development and applied technology, the combination of social production process, scale and effectiveness of material, the natural conditions...

Marx's views on labor productivity are similar to Cobb-Douglas or Solow, saying that science and technology will increase labor productivity in a sustainable way because it is the best way to shorten production time when considering the same product.

According to Marx, increasing labor productivity is the increase in production capacity or labor productivity, which can be understood as a change in the way of labor, changes that shorten the social labor time necessary to produce a commodity, so that the less number of workers can produce more value.

Increasing labor productivity means reducing labor costs per unit of product. In the same time, the higher the productivity, the higher the number of value produce while the creative value is not increased. The higher the labor productivity, the less time it takes to produce a unit of product, resulting in a decrease in the value of that unit of product, a decrease in the price of that product, but not a decrease in the value of its use. Marx wrote: "In general, the greater the productive capacity of a labor, the shorter the indispensable labor time to produce an item and the smaller the labor volume in that product is, less the value of that product. Increasing labor productivity is a general economic rule for all forms of society. But the movement and expression of the law of increasing labor productivity in different social forms are also different, due to different levels of production forces.

3.3. Main methods of calculating labor productivity

There are many ways of measuring productivity such as by product artifacts, by revenue, by marginal products, and by labor time... In the context of it, this paper only mentions to two common ways to measure labor productivity: by product artifacts and by revenue, because these methods show labor productivity in a specific way, not affected by price. It is easy to compare labor productivity of different enterprises or countries when producing the same type of products. Moreover, the method by revenue allows measuring of all products including unfinished products. This is in accordance with the actual situation of the manufacturing enterprises.

3.3.1. Productivity by product artifacts

Measuring by product artifact means measure the quantity of goods in their inherent units. The method of calculating the productivity by product artifacts can be conducted in two ways: by the average product productivity or by the marginal product productivity.

This indicator uses product artifacts of each product to indicate employment productivity of one employee.

Formula: $W = Q/T$

In which: W: labor productivity of one employee Q: Total output in product artifacts

T: Total number of employees

Product artifact means measuring the quantity of goods in its inherent units. For example, a fan is measured by a unit; Cement is measured in tons, kilograms, bags ... depending on the type of product.

Advantages and disadvantages of measuring labor productivity with product artifacts:

- Advantages: This indicator shows labor productivity in a specific way, not affected by price, and it can compare labor productivity of different enterprises or countries when producing the same type of products.

- Disadvantages: This measurement method cannot be used to calculate for all types of products, not suitable for the actual situation of commodity producing enterprises because they usually produce many types of products rather than producing one type of products like before.

Q: The final product should only be counted as the finished product, not the unfinished products; the unfinished product is still in the process of production, so it does not fully reflect the output of employees.

- Scope of application is limited, only applied in the enterprise producing the homogenous product (e.g coal, textiles, oil and gas, agriculture). In an enterprise, this method is only partially applied.

3.3.2. *Productivity calculated by product revenue*

This is a method of calculating productivity according to the ratio of the total value of the product attributed to the monetary unit over the total number of employees. This calculation is relatively popular because it is simple and easy to measure. We also have two ways of calculating productivity, namely with the total value of the average revenue and the total value of revenue margin.

The formula: $W = Q/T$

W: The level of labor productivity

- At the country level:

Q: is calculated in GDP in VND

T: Total number of employees working in the national economy

- At enterprise level:

Q: Value of total output, added value or revenue

+ The value of the total output value of all products include the cost and profit

+ Added value: the new value created

+ Sales revenue is the value after the sale of products

T: employees in the enterprise, day, hour, minute, day/person, hour/person.

- Advantages: This method can be used to calculate productivity for all types of products including unfinished products, which is in accordance with the actual situation of the goods manufacturing enterprises because they often produce many types of products.

- Disadvantages: This indicator shows labor productivity in a non-specific manner, which is affected by price, cannot compare productivity levels of different businesses or countries according to a type of product manufactured. If comparing the same business, the result over the years is not completely accurate, specifically:

+ Not encouraging saving materials and using economical inputs. Enterprises that use a lot of expensive supplies will yield higher labor productivity;

+ Impacted by calculating the total output by the factory method. If the amount of products require much cooperation and joint ventures with external firms, the product structure change will distort the labor productivity of the enterprise itself;

+ Only used in case of product composition remains unchanged or changes little because the change of product composition will distort level and speed of labor productivity growth. When changing from low labor-intensive products to high- labor-intensive products with low value, labor productivity decreases and vice versa;

- Scope of application: It can be widely used, from enterprises to industries and the national economy level. It can be used to compare labor productivity levels between manufacturing enterprises and industries.

3.4. Measures and main determinants of labor productivity at enterprises

3.4.1. Measures labor productivity at enterprises

Labor productivity group: It shows the ability to produce products or services at the lowest possible labor cost. Labor is always considered in relation to other factors. The criteria often used consist of value added on labor costs, labor productivity (value added/number of employees), total output per capita, labor costs per worker action...

Formula: Labor productivity = VA/L

Of which:

VA: Value added = Income (total wages + social welfare expenses + Tax and public charges (all taxes and charges) + Depreciation expenses + Operating profit (Surplus)

VA of specific sectors is calculated in different ways upon on characters of the sectors.

L: Average labors of enterprise in the year. It is calculated by two ways:

+ L = Numbers of labors of 12 months/12

Or L = (Number of labors at 01 January + Number of labors at 31 December)/2

3.4.2. Main determinants of labor productivity at enterprises

Labor productivity of enterprise is affected by factors both internal and external to the firm. Internal factors are typically levers (such as workforce and managerial skills) on which business owners and business managers can act to improve enterprise performance. External factors refer to market, industry and local conditions (e.g. capital, degree of competition, technology development, education level, economies of agglomeration and specialization), which influence productivity growth and productivity diffusion by shaping the incentives and investment choices of business owners. With a view to narrowing down the theme of the paper, the focus is only on the main determinants of enterprises' labor productivity, including: human resource (health, education, and skill), capital resource, institutional policies, innovation (including R&D) and ICT.

Figure 1 offers a synoptic view of some main determinants of labor productivity of enterprises, although the visual is only for clarification purposes since many of the factors interact with each other in the way they affect labor productivity of enterprises. For example, education and skills influence the use of ICT and R&D investments in enterprises. As the results, labor productivity can be improved by technical skills and application of innovation to enterprises.

Based on the above diagram, the most affected factors to labor productivity of enterprises are:

- Human resources (education, skills, health, working attitude). It is one of key factors of production. Human resources encompass all that is needed for labor to produce goods and services. These elements include the expertise, knowledge, training, skills, experience, and any other characteristic needed to create economic value. Human resources are a direct contributor to producing goods and services in all types of economies. Labor is the first and most important factor affecting labor productivity. Labor productivity of each country, industry and enterprise depends largely on the educational level, skills, capacity and health of the labor.

- Capital resource: The term capital resource is an economic concept that refers to man-made elements employed to produce goods or services. They are resources that allow the company to carry on with its productive activities. The difference between these capital resources and the factors of production, which is an economic concept too, is that capital resources point to man-made items, while factors of production refer to both natural and man-made resources (such as land and labor). Capital resources include things like office buildings, manufacturing facilities and machinery in general. An economy benefits when capital resources investment increases because it means that productive output should be increased too, that means a higher level of employment and an overall improvement in the economic system.
- Innovation (R&D) and ICT which has to do with the introduction of new products or processes at the firm level, including through R&D investments. ICT and digitalization, including the use of hardware, e-commerce, and software programs that can be labor productivity professionalize small business management. Besides mainly mentioned determinants, some determinants affect to labor productivity of enterprises are business networks, including participation in clusters and global supply chains that enhance labor productivity to overcome size-related constraints with respect to access to resources and markets; managerial skills and management practices, including those more closely related to the workforce such as training and human resource management; enterprises' cultures that can boost or constrain labor productivity.

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